

Recommendations on Metadata

Describing the data, services and information
you have available

A User Guide provided by the
Centre for Earth Observation Programme of the European Commission

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C E O

P R O G R A M M E

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

This document has been produced by the Centre for Earth Observation (CEO) Programme of the European Commission.

It aims to provide guidance on the way in which your resources (such as datasets, documents, training courses etc) should be described, for the purposes of management of the resources within your organisation and for external advertising of their value to potential customers.

Metadata are becoming an increasingly important part of data and service provider activities. As the number of available datasets and services grows, it is increasingly important that they are described in a consistent manner to allow potential users to easily identify resources of interest and to assess their suitability with respect to their particular needs.

If you wish to ensure wide interest in the resources your organisation offers, the production of metadata describing these resources should be of high priority. Comprehensive metadata are an ideal way of promoting your resources to potential users, and the first step in gaining their confidence in the quality of your organisation's products and services.

1.2 Aims

This document provides recommendations on the way resources (data, products and services) should be described and examples of such descriptions. This document does not introduce a new metadata standard but aims to provide guidelines that are consistent with major international and European metadata standards. This document is not intended towards major data holding organisations, that are already using metadata which presumably fit their needs. It is intended towards small information holders and potential providers that are looking for an efficient and yet comprehensive way to describe and advertise their resources.

It is hoped that the adoption of these guidelines will :

- help you in your internal data management and house-keeping tasks,
- encourage you to provide information on your resources for advertisement via CEO information services.

If you wish to follow the CEO recommendations on metadata, it is strongly recommended that you obtain the CEO Metadata Authoring Tool for Microsoft Windows as this will considerably simplify the process of generating and managing resource descriptions. Information about this tool is provided in section 6 of this document.

1.3 Rationale

CEO initiated this work on metadata as a response to a strong requirement of Earth Observation (EO) users in Europe, as identified in the CEO Pathfinder Phase (see [4]). EO users (and especially small/medium size data providers) asked for guidelines on:

- the need for metadata,
- practices for generation of metadata,
- guidelines for content,
- use of standards.

Users of EO particularly indicated

- their confusion from the large number of existing metadata standards and initiatives,
- their wish that CEO should harmonise its efforts with existing programmes.

CEO first produced a survey of current practices and standards in European Organisations in six different thematic sectors (see [2]), and a survey of European and international standards and initiatives (see [3]). The conclusions of this preparatory work suggested that there already exists a number of dominant standards -DIF, GILS, GEO, Dublin Core, CEN TC 287.

These standards however are either too complicated for a small/medium EO information provider or address only part of the information that (s)he needs to describe.

As a result and based on the surveyed standards, CEO developed this User Guide with recommendations on use of metadata. They are intended for EO users but do not only cover EO data; this is because EO users do not use EO data only.

The recommended metadata can also be used by organisations who internally already described their holdings according to a standard (even proprietary) and wish to create more brief descriptions in order to advertise them in the CEO Enabling Services.

1.4 Contents

Section 2 provides an overview and definitions about metadata and introduces the CEO approach .

Section 3 contains the recommended elements for description of your resources, and example descriptions.

Section 4 provides details of recommended controlled keyword lists and formats for certain element descriptions.

Section 5 provides information about the CEO metadata authoring tool.

Section 6 provides contact details for further information on the CEO programme and specific questions regarding advertisement of your resources.

Section 7 provides references of relevant documentation from CEO.

2 Metadata

2.1 Introduction

This section briefly reviews the main purposes of metadata and explains why the production and maintenance of metadata should be an important part of your organisation's activities.

2.2 Definition and purpose of metadata

Metadata are data about the content, quality, condition and other characteristics of data. There are many other definitions to be found for metadata - 'data about data', or more broadly 'information about information'. For the purposes of these recommendations we assume the practical definition 'a set of information items which describe a resource'.

Most commonly, metadata are generated to describe a dataset, but they may also be used to describe many other resources such as documents, training courses and so on. Groups of metadata 'records', each one describing a specific resource, are grouped into 'catalogues' which may be searched by potential users to identify resources of interest.

Metadata have three principal purposes:

- to catalogue a resource for the purposes of efficient storage and retrieval within your organisation;
- to be used for external advertising of a resource to potential users;
- to describe the details of the format of a resource and the way in which the resource should be used.

This guide pertains to the use of metadata for the first and second purposes, discussed below under the headings of internal management and external advertising. For the third purpose, which is outside the scope of this document, readers can refer to ref. [1].

Readers who are interested to have a broader view on metadata, can refer to [2] and [3].

Internal management

Metadata are an essential component of managing your organisation's resources, for the following reasons:

- to ensure consistency and integrity of information, through efficient house-keeping;
- to provide easy access to information concerning the nature, purpose and current status of the resource;
- to record the processes by which the resource was generated and may be used;
- to record the personnel responsible for generating and maintaining the resource;
- to record the available formats and other supply details for the resource.

External advertising

A major component of the CEO programme is the development of information services to serve the 'non-traditional' user of Earth Observation (EO) related data and services. The resource descriptions produced by data and service providers are the most valuable component of these information services.

Good 'advertising' metadata should contain a clear and concise set of information with the following purposes from the point of view of the potential user. It should:

- allow efficient location of resources which may be of interest;
- allow an assessment of the suitability of a resource with respect to a user's intended application;
- allow an assessment of the cost and relative benefit of the resource and any access or use constraints;
- stimulate initial confidence in the quality of the resources provided by your organisation.

2.3 CEO approach to metadata

Ten (10) simple resource types are identified (see 3.1). Each of the resource types is described using a well defined number of pieces of information termed elements. Each element may be compound (i.e be a structure of sub-elements) or simple.

Elements can either be Descriptive or Administrative. Descriptive elements are those which are appropriate to the description of a resource. Administrative elements apply to the record containing the information and not the information itself.

Most elements can be edited as free text. This allows for maximum flexibility in describing the resource and allows for free-text search. It does not cater however, for spelling mistakes or for dubious semantics. Some elements get their values from pre-defined lists of controlled keywords. Such a list is called a controlled list. Thesaurus in the context of this document, indicates a well-defined and maintained instance of a keyword list. Controlled keywords are chosen from thesauri. CEO controlled lists allow a hierarchical structure of keywords. Uncontrolled keywords are keywords that are not chosen by thesauri but are entered as free text. Uncontrolled keywords can be entered in the element 'Abstract'.

For some elements (or sub-elements), it is mandatory that a value is supplied. Therefore they are characterised as mandatory or optional. Mandatory elements are the ones which are considered important to allow potential users to identify or assess the suitability of a resource for their purposes, or are essential to ensure consistency. Elements that are not mandatory, are optional. Most elements are optional. For certain mandatory elements (or sub-elements), the value 'Not Applicable' may be supplied if no appropriate information can be supplied.

3 Describing your resources

3.1 Resource types

This section contains recommendations for describing the following types of resource.

Section	Resource	Purpose
3.4	Organisation	Provide general information on your organisation, such as services offered and contact details.
3.5	Person	Outline the experience or expertise of an individual.
3.6	Dataset	Describe datasets and other products. This may include EO datasets at any processing level, cartographic datasets, maps, statistics or others.
3.7	Document	Describe textbooks, journal papers, technical reports, user manuals, on line documents etc.
3.8	Service	Describe value adding, consultancy and other services.
3.9	Project	Describe a research project, or a demonstration case that describes a successful application of EO data
3.10	Event	Describe workshops, seminars, conferences, training courses etc.
3.11	Software / model	Describe a software package or model.
3.12	Discussion forum	Describe electronic or other discussion fora.
3.13	Promotion	Describe a special offer, a job opportunity or another special announcement

Table 3.1 : Resource Types

Elements (or sub-elements) can be repeatable or non-repeatable. A repeatable element may be listed a number of times within a metadata record.

Values for some elements are entered in free text, however they have to follow a specific field format. Field formats are discussed in section 4.2.

The CEO metadata are multi-lingual. They allow that resources and their descriptive records are in different languages.

Please see the examples in section 3 for details.

3.2 Describing a resource

It is recommended that each of the resource types listed above is described using a well defined number of pieces of information termed elements.

Two tables are given below, listing *Descriptive* and *Administrative* elements.

- Descriptive elements are those are appropriate to the description of a resource.
- Administrative elements apply to the record containing the information and not the information itself. Administrative elements apply to all resource types, and for economy of space, they are not repeated for every resource.

The recommended descriptive and administrative elements are listed in the following tables.

Descriptive element	Purpose
Title	A short title for the resource which is clear to the potential user (eg organisation or dataset name).
Organisation	The name of the organisation which supplies the resource.
Abstract	Brief description of the content and purpose of the resource.
Point of contact	Details for the person who should be contacted for further details of the resource.
Language of resource	Specify the language of the resource if appropriate.
Author	List the authors of a document etc.
Controlled subject index	This should consist of a set of 'keywords' selected from a controlled list, used to specify the subject of the content of a resource. An example would be the parameters which a dataset contains or the discipline to which a document is relevant.
Spatial Coverage	The regions of the earth to which a resource is applicable. This might be the location of an organisation or the coverage of a dataset.
Temporal Coverage	This should be used to specify the time relevance of a resource, for example an event might take place on a certain day, or a dataset might be available over a number of years.
Cross Reference	Use this element to list information on other related resources and details of how they may be obtained.
Original Resource Identifier	Specify an associated identifier eg a internal document reference/ISBN.
Scale	Specify the scale of a dataset.
Resolution	Specify the resolution of a dataset.
Method/Quality	Specify method of production of the resource and quality procedures applied.
Supply details	Outline the means by which the resource may be obtained, delivery format and costs.
Constraints	List and constraints on access to or use of the resource.
Publisher	Specify the publisher of a resource.
Version	Specify the version of a resource.
Publication Date	Specify the publication date of a resource.

Table 3.2 : Descriptive elements

Administrative element	Purpose
Record Identifier	Specify a unique identifier amongst your organisation's resource descriptions.
	The combination of a unique record identifier and unique record provider allows you to uniquely identify any resource description.
Resource Type	Specify the resource type, ie dataset, document. The resource type determines which descriptive elements are relevant for a given resource (see table 3.4).
Language of Record	Specify the language used in the descriptive record, not the resource itself.
Record Provider	This field is relevant if you are maintaining records provided by a number of different organisations, eg sectors of your company, it should be a recognised identifier for the organisation providing the resource description. The default value is the 'Organisation' value.
Record Creation Date	Specify the date of first creation of the description.
Record Last Modification date	Specify the date of last modification of the description.
Record Expiry date	Specify the date at which the validity of the description expires. This can be used for maintenance purposes to ensure that irrelevant descriptions are deleted.

Table 3.3 : Administrative elements

The elements which are applicable to each resource are summarised in the following table. It is recommended that the completion of certain elements is made mandatory for each particular resource type to ensure that useful descriptions are obtained. These are described in detail in sections 3.5 to 3.14.

Element applicability

The table below indicates the elements which are applicable to each resourcetype.

	Organisation	Person	Dataset	Document	Service	Project	Event	Software/Model	Discussion Forum	Promotion
Descriptive										
Title	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Organisation		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Abstract	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Point of contact	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Language of resource	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	
Author			✓	✓		✓		✓		
Controlled subject index	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Spatial Coverage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Temporal Coverage			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Cross Reference	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Original Resource Identifier			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Scale			✓							
Resolution			✓							
Method/Quality			✓							
Supply details			✓	✓				✓		
Constraints			✓	✓				✓		
Publisher				✓						
Version				✓						
Publication Date				✓						
Administrative										
Record Identifier	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Resource Type	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Language of Record	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Record Provider	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Record Creation Date	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Record Last Modification date	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Record Expiry date	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3.4 : Element applicability matrix

3.3 Key

Each element may have a number of *sub-elements* which define the way in which the required information should be presented to aid clarity. These are presented in the following table. Please also see the examples in the following sections for details.

Mandatory and repeatable sub-elements

(M) Indicates an item which is mandatory (ie must be completed). These fields are those which are considered important to allow potential users to identify or assess the suitability of a resource for their purposes, or are essential to ensure consistency.

For certain mandatory elements / sub-elements the value 'Not Applicable' may be supplied if you cannot supply appropriate information. For example, element 'Spatial Coverage' might be meaningful and have a value for a document about Indonesia, but is not applicable for the document that you are currently reading.

(R) Indicates that an element / sub-element is repeatable, ie it may be listed a number of times within a metadata record. For example a dataset may be relevant to a number of disciplines, or contain measurements of a number of physical parameters, each of which should be listed.

If a sub-element is mandatory and repeatable, you must specify at least one item. If no symbol is presented the sub-element is neither mandatory nor repeatable.

Controlled lists

For certain items it is recommended that the contents are selected from a list of 'controlled keywords'. Information about these lists is given in section 4.1. The CEO maintains and updates these lists regularly. Please see section 6 for details on obtaining current versions.

Thesaurus in the context of this document, indicates a well-defined and maintained list of validated keywords. These keywords are called *controlled keywords* and are chosen from thesauri. *Uncontrolled keywords* are keywords that are not chosen from thesauri but are entered as free text in the element 'Abstract'.

Field formats

Date and spatial location elements should be specified in a particular field format to ensure clarity. Details of recommended field formats are contained in section 4.2.

3.4 Element structure and format

Descriptive elements	Structure	Notes
Title		
Organisation		
Abstract		Allow a 'free text' description
Point of contact	Contact Name (M) Contact Position Contact Organisation Name Contact Address Contact Country Contact Telephone Contact Fax Contact email address (M) Contact URL Contact Other	For 'Contact email address', value 'Not Applicable' is allowed.
Language of resource	Controlled List: Language (M) • Thesaurus (M) • Controlled Keyword (M,R)	The name of one thesaurus should be specified. Multiple keyword selections from this single thesaurus are allowed.
Author		

Controlled subject index	<p>Cross-Type Controlled List: Discipline (M)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thesaurus (M) • Controlled Keyword (M,R) <p>Type-Specific Controlled List: <name> (M)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thesaurus (M) • Controlled Keyword (M,R) 	<p>The cross-type list applies to all resources and is a selection from the list of controlled Discipline keywords</p> <p>The type-specific lists are different for each resource and are described in the section appropriate to each resource. In each case you should list the source and version number of any thesaurus from which keywords are chosen.</p> <p>For 'Controlled subject index', value 'Not Applicable' is allowed.</p>
Spatial Coverage	<p>Geo Point</p> <p>Bounding Rectangle</p> <p>Bounding Polygon</p> <p>Circular Coverage</p> <p>Location (R)</p>	<p>If applicable, one sub-element must be supplied.</p> <p>Only Location names can be repeated, using multiple selections from a single controlled list.</p> <p>The other items may be used to specify a bounding shape for spatial coverage.</p> <p>For 'Spatial Coverage', value 'Not Applicable' is allowed.</p>
Temporal Coverage	<p>Temporal Range: (M,R)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start Date (M) • End Date <p>Temporal Coverage - Textual</p>	<p>The 'Temporal Range' is a repeatable sub-element to allow a number of periods of coverage, eg a yearly workshop.</p> <p>Use an empty End Date to specify an indefinite period.</p> <p>'Temporal Coverage - Textual' allows a 'free text' description.</p> <p>For 'Temporal Coverage', value 'Not Applicable' is allowed.</p>
Cross Reference	<p>Cross Reference Title</p> <p>Cross Reference Linkage</p> <p>Cross Reference Type</p>	<p>The 'Linkage' field should be used to list a URL or other locator for the resource if applicable.</p>
Original Resource Identifier		
Scale	<p>Controlled List: Scale (M)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thesaurus (M) • Controlled Keyword (M,R) 	<p>For 'Scale', value 'Not Applicable' is allowed.</p>
Resolution		<p>Allow a 'free text' description</p>

Method/Quality	Data acquisition process Processing History Quality Accuracy Completeness	Each of the sub-elements is a free text description.
Supply details		Allows for a 'free text' description
Constraints	Access Use	Each of the sub-elements allows for a 'free text' description
Publisher		
Version		
Publication Date		Date format (section 4.2.1)
Administrative elements		
Record Identifier		
Resource Type		One of the CEO resource types, ie dataset, document.
Language of Record	Controlled List: Language (M) • Thesaurus (M) • Controlled Keyword (M,R)	Select from a controlled list.
Record Provider		
Record Creation Date		Date format (section 4.2.1)
Record Last Modification date		Date format (section 4.2.1)
Record Expiry date		Date format (section 4.2.1)

3.5 Organisation

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		Name of the organisation
Abstract		You should provide the 'mission statement' for your organisation, ie a short description of its main purpose. You may also provide a more detailed description of your organisation and any additional information of interest. It may also be advantageous to provide details of the services which your organisation provides.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Language of resource (M,R)		List the languages in which services may be provided by your organisation
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Organisation Type (section 4.1.9)
Spatial Coverage (M)		Give the location of your organisation.
Cross Reference (R)		

Example

Title	A Company Ltd
Abstract	<p>To provide quality InfraRed satellite data to the European market and develop applications for the data.</p> <p>We are based in Bristol, UK, with branch offices in Darmstadt and Kiruna. We have 50 employees in total, 25 of which have a University degree in a remote sensing related subject.</p> <p>The company has been in business since 1991, and there has been steady growth in number of employees and turnover to date.</p> <p>A Company Ltd provide data passive IR satellite data processed up to level 3 and develop applications for the data.</p> <p>We provide a number of on line services giving guidance on our data product catalogue and other services.</p>
Point of contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith Contact Position: Head of the marketing division Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol Contact Country: UK Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901 Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902 Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk Contact URL: http://www.acompany.co.uk Contact Other: Enquiries of any nature are welcome at all times.</p>
Language of Resource	<p>Controlled List: Language Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0 Controlled Keyword: English Controlled Keyword: French Controlled Keyword: German</p>

Controlled
subject index

Controlled List: Discipline
Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0
Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Applications
Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Data Provision
Controlled List: Organisation
Thesaurus: CEO Organisation Type version 1.0
Controlled Keyword: Data provider
Controlled Keyword: Application developer

Spatial Coverage

Controlled List: Location
Thesaurus: GCMD Location Keywords v2.3
Controlled Keyword: Country>United Kingdom>Bristol
Controlled Keyword: Country>Sweden>Kiruna
Controlled Keyword: Country>Germany>Darmstadt

Cross Reference

Cross Reference Title: A Company Home Page
Cross Reference Linkage: <http://www.acompany.co.uk>
Cross Reference Type: Hypertext Documents

3.6 Person

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		Name of the person
Organisation		
Abstract		Outline the responsibility or role which the person has. You may also outline the services or expertise which the person provides.
Point of contact (M)		
Language of resource (M,R)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		

Example

Title	Peter Smith of A Company Ltd
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>Peter Smith is the head of the marketing division of A Company Ltd and is responsible for all marketing activities of the company. He has been with the company since its beginning in 1991.</p> <p>Peter Smith has an MSc in Geography, and is an expert in remote sensing. He also holds an MBA with emphasis on technical marketing. He is experienced in the development and marketing of the SSTMaps product line. He is also the author of the book 'Geographic Information Systems and Remote Sensing' (see cross-reference resource).</p>
Point of contact	Contact Name: Peter Smith
Contact Position:	<p>Head of the marketing division</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol</p> <p>Contact Country: UK</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p> <p>Contact URL: http://www.acompany.co.uk</p> <p>Contact Other: Enquiries of any nature are welcome at all times.</p>
Language of Resource	<p>Controlled List: Language</p> <p>Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: English</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: French</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Applications</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Data Provision</p>

Spatial Coverage

Controlled List: Location

Thesaurus: GCMD Location Keywords v2.3

Controlled Keyword: Country>United Kingdom>Bristol

Cross Reference

Cross Reference Title: Geographic Information Systems
and Remote Sensing'

Cross Reference Linkage: Contact us for details.

Cross Reference Type: Book

3.7 Dataset

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		Include a note of the potential applications of the dataset.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Author		Creator of the dataset
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2)
	Type Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Parameter (section 4.1.3). Dataset Type (section 4.1.5).
Spatial Coverage (M)		For spatial data, specify either a point, or bounding shape for the contents of the dataset. It is suggested that a location keyword is used if this is more appropriate. See section 4.2.1 for format details.
Temporal Coverage (M)		For non-continuous datasets, it is recommended that this item be used to specify the start and end date of the coverage. See section 4.2.1 for format details.
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		
Scale (M)		Express the scale of the dataset by choosing a scale from the 'scale' controlled list (see section 4.1.10)
Resolution		Express in free text the resolution in a format relevant to the type of dataset and the discipline.

<p>Method/Quality</p>	<p>Data acquisition process Processing history Quality Accuracy Completeness</p>	<p>Provide a short description of the method by which the base data was collected, eg in-situ, airborne photography, satellite.</p> <p>List the primary steps involved in creation of the product and the names of any algorithms used.</p> <p>Describe any quality procedures applied to the dataset. Include indicators of data quality, standard methods used and recognised or potential problems with quality.</p> <p>Established quality control mechanisms should be listed and references to calibration/validation datasets or models should be made.</p> <p>Provide a brief outlines of the accuracy of the dataset contents.</p> <p>Describe the completeness of the dataset, eg 'complete', 'partial', etc.</p>
<p>Supply details</p>		<p>Describe the order process, available formats and costs of each. List any concessions for academic/non-profit use.</p>
<p>Constraints</p>	<p>Access Use</p>	<p>Describe any constraints on access to or use of the data. If there are none, please specify 'None'.</p>

Example

Title	Sea surface temperature maps of the Mediterranean (SSTMaps)
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>This product forms part of a wider scheme to assess the state of the Mediterranean ocean. It may be combined with water run-off data, pollution data and fisheries statistics.</p> <p>The data set has been used for a number by fishing fleets to plan catch routes, and has resulted in improved efficiency of operations.</p>
Point of contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Data</p> <p>Controlled List: Dataset type</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Dataset Type version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Surface Map 2D</p> <p>Controlled List: Parameter</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Parameter version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Sea Surface Temperature</p>
Spatial coverage	<p>Controlled List: Location</p> <p>Thesaurus: GCMD Location Keywords v2.3</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Ocean_or_Sea>Mediterranean Sea</p>
Temporal Coverage	<p>Temporal Range: Start Date: 1986-01-01</p> <p>End Date:</p> <p>Temporal Coverage - Textual:</p>
Scale	Scale: 1:5000-1:25000

Resolution	Resolution: 1 km x 1 km
Method/Quality	<p>Quality: Our datasets are validated to the highest standards (Ref XYZ 12345), as we operate a comprehensive quality assurance program.</p> <p>Extensive procedures data ingestion, processing and output formatting are in operation. We are also an ISO9000 registered organisation.</p> <p>Accuracy: Our data products are accurate to within one degree K. Please contact us for further details.</p>
Supply details	<p>Products may be ordered on an ad-hoc basis, although discounts are available for subscription services.</p> <p>Single images are priced at 400 ECU, subscriptions are available for 3-monthly periods as a minimum at a 10% reduction, or a "bulk-buy" scheme of 200 images is available at a 5% reduction. Images can be supplied in a number of formats and may be distributed on CD-ROM or over the internet by ftp after registration.</p> <p>Please contact the A Company helpdesk for further information.</p>
Constraints	<p>Access: Please register with us as authorised user before attempting access.</p> <p>Use: None.</p>

3.8 Document

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		
Point of contact (M,R)		
Language of resource (M,R)		
Author (M)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Document Type (section 4.1.6)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Temporal Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		
Publisher		Provide the name of the publisher.
Version		Provide the version number or edition of the document.
Publication Date (M)		
Supply details		
Constraints	Access Use	

Example

Title	Geographic Information Systems and Remote Sensing
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	The aim of the book is to present a broad overview of how the two areas of GIS and Remote Sensing interact using applications.
Point of contact	Contact Name: Peter Smith Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol Contact Country: UK Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk
Language of Resource	Controlled List: Language Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0 Controlled Keyword: English
Controlled subject index	Controlled List: Discipline Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0 Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing Controlled List: Document Type Thesaurus: CEO Document Type Version 1.0 Controlled Keyword: Textbook
Spatial Coverage	Not Applicable
Temporal Coverage	Not Applicable
Author	Peter Smith, A Company Ltd
Original Resource Identifier	ISBN X-XXX-XXXXX-X
Publisher	Published by The Publisher Ltd, London, England.
Supply details	Available from publishers or bookshops in the UK and Europe. Cost 50 ECU. Available to registered students at half-price.

3.9 Service

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		
Point of contact (M,R)		
Language of resource (M,R)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2)
	Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Service Type (section 4.1.7)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Temporal Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		

Example

Title	Remote sensing and GIS consultancy
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>A Company is able to provide a wide range of services to a varied customer base. In recent years we have completed projects in Oceanography, Space and Remote Sensing, Cartography and GIS.</p> <p>We have expertise in many disciplines and are always willing to consider new areas. We pride our selves on the ability to satisfy customers with a wide variety of requirements. For a more specific quote please contact the address below.</p>
Point of contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol</p> <p>Contact Country: UK</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p> <p>Contact URL: http://www.acompany/co.uk</p> <p>Contact Other: Enquiries of any nature are welcome at all times.</p>
Language of resource	<p>Controlled List: Language</p> <p>Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: English</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: French</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: German</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing</p> <p>Controlled List: Service type</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Service Type Version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Consultancy</p>
Spatial Coverage	Not Applicable
Temporal Coverage	Not Applicable

3.10 Project

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		Describe the methods used in the project and list any datasets used as input data. Outline the results of the project, including output products, customer opinion and the overall cost/benefit of the project etc. Include contact names and of participating organisations, eg customer contact points, scientific referees or data providers.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Author		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Project type (section 4.1.11)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Temporal Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		

Example

Title	Monitoring potato crops using satellite earth observation data
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>The project has developed maps of the UK's potato crop to be used for area control within the existing levy system.</p> <p>The project also developed a series of image processing techniques which are systematically applied to satellite imagery collected over the growing season. Outputs result in an accurate crop assessment available for use in late-August / early-September.</p> <p>The satellite data system uses image processing and classification techniques based on multi-temporal, supervised maximum likelihood algorithms. This is linked to a GIS which contains information provided by the individual farmers, along with 1:25,000 maps which are used as a backdrop for classification outputs.</p> <p>The potato monitoring system is now in the 3rd year of operation. Areas surveyed are flexible and can be extended to cover a more extensive region. The use of satellite technology for crop finding has potential spin-offs in areas such as crop estimates, crop health and development monitoring, and precision farming.</p> <p>Cost/benefit analysis</p> <p>The potato monitoring system can be applied at an annual cost of X ECU per km², based on Y survey areas. Substantial savings are enabled through better managed and reduced staff costs. Avoidance of levy payments is less likely if a credible checking procedure is known to be available to the collecting authority.</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>Customer: Alan Thompson, Potato Funding Council Data provider: Peter Smith, A Company Ltd</p>
Point of contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Applications</p>

Controlled List: Project type
Thesaurus: CEO Project Type version 1.0
Controlled Keyword: Application demonstrator
Controlled Keyword: Operational system

Spatial Coverage

Controlled List: Location
Thesaurus: GCMD Location Keywords v2.3
Controlled Keyword: Continent>Europe>United Kingdom

Temporal Coverage

Temporal Range: Start Date: 1994-05-01
End Date: 1994-09-30

Temporal Range: Start Date: 1995-05-01
End Date: 1995-09-30

Temporal Range: Start Date: 1996-05-01
End Date: 1996-09-30

Temporal Coverage - Textual: Surveys to date cover summer periods (May to September) over the years from 1994 to 1996

3.11 Event

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		Describe the purpose of the event, including specific aims. Describe the content of the event, including speakers /lecturers and other information of relevance. Outline the level of the event academic content if appropriate. List any pre-requisite knowledge or training requirements. Include registration details.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Language of resource (M,R)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Event Type (section 4.1.8)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Temporal Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		

Example

Title	19th International Workshop on Information Systems
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>The aim of the workshop is to gather as much information as possible on a wide range of topics relating to new developments in information systems. The full list of participants is still under negotiation but as soon as this is known, this list will be updated and made available.</p> <p>Register by contacting A Company, or on-line via a link from the company web page. The cost is 300 ECU plus accommodation. Further details of the workshop program are available from the company web page or by contacting us.</p> <p>In order to participate in the workshop a reasonable level of knowledge about Information Systems is required. No specific qualifications are required.</p>
Point of Contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol</p> <p>Contact Country: UK</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p> <p>Contact URL: http://www.acompany.co.uk</p>
Language of Resource	<p>Controlled List: Language</p> <p>Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: English</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing</p> <p>Controlled List: Event type</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Event Type version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Workshop</p>

Spatial Coverage **Controlled List: Location**
 Thesaurus: GCMD Location Keywords v2.3
 Controlled Keyword: Europe>Germany>Berlin

Temporal Coverage **Temporal range: Start Date: 1997-02-11**
 End Date: 1997-02-13
 Temporal Coverage - Textual:

3.12 Software / Model

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		Summarise the purpose of the package, module or method. List any requirements or recommendations for operating system, processor speed, system memory, disk space etc.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Author		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Software/Model type (section 4.1.12) Parameter (section 4.1.3)
Spatial Coverage (M)		
Temporal Coverage (M)		
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		
Supply details		
Constraints	Access Use	

This resource type should be used to describe packages, modules, methods, generic algorithms or models as follows:

- Package: a software suite providing a complete environment for problem solving across a range of applications. Each package consists of a number of modules.
- Module: a set of related methods for the solution to a specific problem set. For example a classification module might include a number of different methods.

- **Method:** a single routine which performs a specific operation.
- **Algorithm:** a well-defined mathematical or statistical procedure, such as a vegetation classification algorithm.
- **Model:** a simplified mathematical representation of a real world system, for example a canopy reflectance or soil erosion model.

Example

Title	REMPACK - Remote sensing image processing package
Organisation	Remote Sensing Graphics Corporation (Short Name: REMGRAPH)
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0 Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Software</p> <p>Controlled List: Software/model type Thesaurus: CEO Software/model type version 1.0 Controlled Keyword: GIS package Controlled Keyword: Image processing tools</p>
Abstract	<p>Platform: Intel, Sun, HP</p> <p>Operating System: Windows 95, Windows NT, Solaris v5</p> <p>Minimum disk space for installation 100 MB, recommended minimum memory requirements 32MB (64MB for optimal performance on NT workstation).</p> <p>Contents: REMGRAPH is a vector- and raster-based GIS package with the following functionality:</p> <p>Input - input routines for image conversion from a number of standard formats</p> <p>Analysis - data manipulation and analysis of images and image combination/overlay etc.</p>

Output - output routines for map and report production.

There are many modules within the REMGRAPH package. The modules which are currently included in the system are:

'REM format conversion', 'REM area and perimeter conversions', 'REM spatial analysis and trend surfaces' and 'REM models and potential surfaces'. See the adverts for these specific routines for more detail.

Point of Contact

Contact Name: Arthur Pewty

Contact Organisation Name: Remote Sensing
Graphics Corporation

Contact Address: 12 5th Street, Dallas

Contact Country: USA

Contact Telephone: 001 234 567 8901

Contact Fax: 001 234 567 8902

Contact E-mail address: arthur.pewty@remgraph.org

Contact URL: <http://www.remgraph.org>

Spatial Coverage

Not Applicable

Temporal Coverage

Not Applicable

Cross Reference

Cross Reference Title: Associated REMGRAPH software modules

Cross Reference Linkage: <http://www.remgraph.org/rempack/modules.htm>

Cross Reference Type: Hypertext documents

Supply details

The package is available as single and multiple user licences.

Discounts are available for academic users.

Please contact us for further details of current prices and stockists.

Constraints

Access: None.

Use: REMGRAPH place no restrictions on use of the package.

3.13 Discussion Forum

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		
Point of contact (M,R)		
Language of resource (M,R)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2)
	Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Forum Type (section 4.1.13)
Cross Reference (R)		

Example

Title	Position representation standard discussion forum
Organisation	A Company Ltd (Short Name: A Company)
Abstract	<p>This discussion forum aims to stimulate debate on the requirements for a new geographic positioning standard.</p> <p>Commercial, scientific and governmental organisations are invited to participate.</p> <p>The particular issues of interest are potential incompatibilities with existing standards, and any particular concerns over the effort needed to bring archived data up to a level compatible with any new standard.</p>
Point of Contact	<p>Contact Name: Peter Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Address: 12 Long Street, Bristol</p> <p>Contact Country: UK</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact Fax: 00 44 1234 567 8902</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: peter.smith@acompany.co.uk</p> <p>Contact URL: http://www.acompany.co.uk</p>
Language of Resource	<p>Controlled List: Language</p> <p>Thesaurus: ISO 639 Language names v1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: English</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Standards>Geographic Information Systems</p> <p>Controlled List: Forum Type</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Forum Type version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Listserver</p>
Cross Reference	<p>Cross Reference Title: Position representation listserver</p> <p>Cross Reference Linkage: http://www.acompany.co.uk/position.htm.</p> <p>Cross Reference Type: Listserver</p>

3.14 Promotion

Element	Sub-elements	Notes
Title (M)		
Organisation		
Abstract		Include a description of the offer, or details about the job opportunity, or other information depending on the case.
Point of contact (M,R)		
Controlled subject index (M)	Cross-Type Controlled List (M,R) Type-Specific Controlled List (M,R)	Discipline (section 4.1.2) Promotion Type (section 4.1.14)
Temporal Coverage (M)		Specify the period for which the offer is available.
Cross Reference (R)		
Original Resource Identifier		

This resource type should be used to describe

- Special offer: announcement about products and services that are provided at special discounts or under other attractive terms
- Job opportunity: announcement of a job opportunity, including details about job type, salary, applicant requirements, applicant restrictions for a job description
- Other promotional messages

Examples

Title	Project manager for oil spill services
Organisation	Short Name: A Company
Abstract	<p>A Company seek an experienced project manager. Great emphasis is put upon international experience. Language skills are beneficial, but the working language will be English.</p> <p>The person appointed must have a solid technical education, and at least five years of experience of project management.</p> <p>The responsibilities of the job offered is to manage a value-adding research project for SAR imagery. The SAR images shall be used to detect oil spill in the coastal waters of Norway, Ireland, UK and Spain.</p> <p>The project will be executed over a period of 2 years, and A Company has the prime contract. The total value of the contract is 2 MECU. A total staff of 12 people is involved in the consortia.</p> <p>The working place will be at our premises in Bristol, UK.</p> <p>Salary will be 20 000 UK pounds per year, including participation in a pension fund and 6 weeks of paid holidays.</p>
Point of Contact	<p>Contact Name: John Smith</p> <p>Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd</p> <p>Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901</p> <p>Contact E-mail address: Not Applicable</p>
Controlled subject index	<p>Controlled List: Discipline</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Applications</p> <p>Controlled List: Promotion Type</p> <p>Thesaurus: CEO Promotion Type version 1.0</p> <p>Controlled Keyword: Job Opportunity</p>
Temporal Coverage	Not Applicable

Title 25% reduction on SST-Maps products

Organisation Short Name: A Company

Abstract This offer is a special introduction offer to new customers.
 We also offer free advice on how you can incorporate this product into your systems, and we have a suite of software for the product (see Readsolt from A Company). For further details, see the description of the SSTMaps product.

Point of Contact Contact Name: John Smith
 Contact Organisation Name: A Company Ltd
 Contact Telephone: 00 44 1234 567 8901
 Contact E-mail address: Not Applicable

Controlled subject index Controlled List: Discipline
 Thesaurus: CEO Discipline version 1.0
 Controlled Keyword: Remote Sensing>Data
 Controlled List: Promotion type
 Thesaurus: CEO Promotion Type version 1.0
 Controlled Keyword: Special Offer

Temporal Coverage Temporal Range : Start Date: 1998-01-01
 End Date: 1998-02-31
 Temporal Coverage - Textual: This offer is not on a regular basis

Cross Reference Cross Reference Title: Product Special Offers
 Cross Reference Linkage: <http://www.acompany.co.uk/products.htm>
 Cross Reference Type: Hypertext document

4 Controlled keywords and formats

4.1 Controlled keywords

It is recommended that certain elements are chosen from a list of controlled 'keywords' (also called valids) maintained by CEO. This section contains a brief summary of the purpose, structure and contents of each list.

These lists have been developed in consultation with a number of provider organisations and are designed to promote consistency in the selection of keywords describing similar resources, such that the accuracy of a user's search for appropriate resources is increased. These lists were based as much as possible, on work already done by international standardisation bodies such as ISO.

As new disciplines, countries, services etc. appear, these lists will inevitably evolve. If you wish to specify an additional keyword to any of the current lists or propose to modify an existing one, please contact the CEO as outlined in Section 6.

4.1.1 Location

(element 'Spatial Coverage')

The location list provides a set of keywords which should be used to specify a geographic location. This may be used to outline the coverage of a data product or similar resource which is specific to a particular location.

'Location keywords' do not only indicate Country. They cover Region, Continent, Country, Dependency, Ocean_or_Sea, Vertical_Location and Extraterrestrial_Location.

Examples

- Country>United Kingdom>Bristol
- Country>Greece>Xanthi
- Continent>Europe>Germany
- Ocean_or_Sea>Mediterranean Sea

For the current full controlled list please contact the CEO.

4.1.2 Discipline

(element 'Controlled subject index • Cross-type controlled list')

This controlled list provides a set of commonly used keywords to specify a discipline which is appropriate to a resource. Users searching for a particular resource may often specify a discipline and/or sub-discipline to focus their search, thus it is recommended that discipline/sub-discipline keywords are provided where relevant.

The discipline/sub-discipline keyword set is hierarchical in nature and levels of the hierarchy are indicated by the '>' symbol. This format allows the user to specify either a broad or narrow search when attempting to locate resources of interest, by specifying a search term at the desired level.

Examples

- Geological maps>Digital Cartographic Model
- Remote Sensing>Data Provision
- Remote Sensing>Applications

For the current controlled list please contact the CEO.

4.1.3 Parameter

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Dataset' or 'Software/model')

It is recommended that certain descriptions include a list of relevant parameter names selected from a controlled list. This may apply to scientific, socio-economic and other types of dataset or software packages and models.

The CEO controlled parameter keywords are hierarchical in nature and levels of the hierarchy are indicated by the '>' symbol. This format allows

the user to specify either a broad or narrow search when attempting to locate resources of interest, by specifying a search term at the desired level.

Parameter keywords should be specified using a 'Category>Topic>Term>Variable> Detailed Variable' scheme. It is not necessary to specify all levels in the hierarchy above 'Variable' if a particular variable is relevant to a number of terms, topics or category. Additional detail may be specified by specifying a 'Detailed Variable' below the level of Variable.

Examples

- Sea Surface Temperature

For the current controlled list please contact the CEO.

4.1.4 Language

(elements 'Language of Resource' and 'Language of Record')

In some cases it is necessary to specify a language (or multiple languages) which are relevant to the contents of a dataset, document, event or other appropriate resource. It is recommended that languages be specified using the ISO 639 standard language names.

Examples

- English
- Italian
- French
- Greek

For the current list please contact the CEO.

4.1.5 Dataset type

(element 'Controlled subject index •Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Dataset')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the dataset types specified

in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a dataset suited to a particular purpose.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Geological maps
- Digital Cartographic Model
- Digital Elevation Model
- Digital Landscape Model
- Inventory
- Orthophoto map
- Atmospheric profile
- Register of geodetic points
- Register of land
- Satellite derived product
- Satellite imagery
- Raster map
- Vector map
- Statistical product
- Aerial photograph
- Statistics

4.1.6 Document type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Document')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the document types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a document suited to a particular purpose.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Textbook
- Chapter
- Journal paper
- Journal Article
- Review article
- On-line document
- Technical note
- Programmer's manual
- Newspaper article
- User manual

4.1.7 Service type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Service')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the service types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a service which suits a particular purpose.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Application development
- Data validation
- Software development
- Consultancy
- Value-added
- Advertising
- Document preparation
- Technical authoring

4.1.8 Event type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Event')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the event types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for an event of particular interest.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Workshop
- Exhibition
- Seminar
- Training course
- Symposium
- Conference
- Discussion Meeting
- Tradeshow

4.1.9 Organisation type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Organisation')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the organisation types specified in descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a organisation with particular expertise.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Data provider
- Consultancy

- Application developer
- Information provider
- Standards body
- Co-ordination body
- Research institution
- Software developer
- Technical author

4.1.10 Scale

(element 'Scale')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the scale formats that will in turn allow users to search for information of the desired scale.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- 1-1:500
- 1:500-1:5000
- 1:5000-1:25000
- 1:25000-1:50000
- 1:50000-1:250000

4.1.11 Project Type

(element 'Controlled subject • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Project')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the projects and demonstration cases specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a project of particular interest.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- European R&D project
- National project
- CEO Demonstration case study

4.1.12 Software / model type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Software/model')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the software / model types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a software, algorithm or model of particular interest.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Package
- Module
- Method
- Algorithm
- Model

4.1.13 Discussion Forum type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Discussion Forum')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the Discussion Forum types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a Discussion Forum of particular interest.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Mailing List Server
- Electronic Bulletin Board
- Newsgroup

4.1.14 Promotion type

(element 'Controlled subject index • Type-specific controlled list' for type = 'Software/model')

This list is maintained to ensure consistency in the promotion types specified in resource descriptions, such that users may be able to specify an agreed type when searching for a promotional announcement of particular interest.

Example keywords are given below. For the current list please contact the CEO.

Examples

- Special offer
- Job Opportunity

4.2 Field Formats

Field format specify the format that has to be followed when a user edits in free text mode information in particular fields. Field formats are not to be confused with data formats that specify how information is stored and manipulated by computers.

For example, for the 5th of May 1998 '1998-03-05' is the recommended field format and 'integer' the data format.

A fixed field format is recommended for specifying the contents of the following items:

- date;
- latitude/longitude;

Details of these formats are given below.

4.2.1 Date/time

The ISO 8601 standard for specifying numeric representations of date and time is recommended where dates and times are specified.

Date

The international standard date notation is 'YYYY-MM-DD', where 'YYYY' is the year in the usual Gregorian calendar, 'MM' is the month of the year between 01 (January) and 12 (December), and 'DD' is the day of the month between 01 and 31.

Open periods should be expressed as using a blank 'End Date' value. Periods of a single day should be expressed with identical Start Date and End Date values.

Time

The international standard notation for the time of day is 'hh:mm:ss', where hh is the number of complete hours that have passed since midnight (00-24), mm is the number of complete minutes that have passed since the start of the hour (00-59), and ss is the number of

seconds since the start of the minute (00-60). The hour value 24 is only possible when the minute and second values are zero.

Time Zone

If no modifiers are present, a date and time as written above is assumed to be in your local time zone. In order to indicate that a time is measured in Universal Time (UTC), you should append a capital letter Z to a time as in '23:59:59Z' or '2359Z'.

The Z represents the 'zero meridian' at Greenwich, London, UK. Universal Time was called Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) before 1972, however this term should no longer be used.

The strings '+hh:mm', '+hhmm', or '+hh' can be added to the time to indicate that the used local time zone is hh hours and mm minutes ahead of UTC. For time zones west of the zero meridian, which are behind UTC, the notation '-hh:mm', '-hhmm', or '-hh' is used instead. For example, Central European Time (CET) is +0100 and U.S./Canadian Eastern Standard Time (EST) is -0500.

Examples

The fourth day of February 1995 is written in standard notation as '1995-02-04'

A training course running from the 4th to the 5th of March 1998 would be specified as '1998-03-04, 1998-03-05'.

An example local time is '23:59:59'.

The following strings all represent the same point in time: '13:45Z' = '15:55+02:00' = '0845-0500'.

4.2.2 Latitude/longitude

For specifying a position it is recommended that Latitude and Longitude co-ordinates are used.

Latitude is measured North or South of the Equator, resulting in a range of -90.0 degrees (S pole) to +90.0 degrees (N pole). Longitude is measured West or East of the Greenwich meridian (in range -180.0 to +180.0 degrees). It is recommended that a standard format of '±XX.X' for latitude and '±XXX.X' for longitude, and lat-long pairs are expressed using the format '±XX.X, ±XXX.X;'. Decimals express minutes (0-59).

Bounding rectangles for spatial coverage should be specified by listing the north-west and, south-east bounding points of coverage.

Bounding polygons should be specified in a clock-wise and closing manner.

Note that spatial coverage may be such that the southernmost latitude may be in the northern hemisphere. Likewise the northernmost latitude may be in the southern hemisphere, westernmost longitude may be in the eastern hemisphere, and easternmost longitude may be in the western hemisphere.

Global dataset coverage is therefore represented by '+90.0,-180.0; -90.0,+180.0'.

5 The CEO metadata authoring tool

The CEO makes available a 'metadata authoring tool' which greatly increases the ease of production and management of resource descriptions. The authoring tool also automatically produces on-line adverts which may be sent to the CEO. These adverts will be put for free on the CEO on-line information system (the CEO Enabling Services) where your resources will be advertised and be promoted to potential customers.

The CEO metadata authoring tool runs on Microsoft Windows. To get a free copy of the tool or for further information regarding the tool contact the CEO (see section 6).

6 CEO information services

If you require further information on the contents of this document, or have any suggestions, please contact the CEO help-desk as follows.

By e-mail to ceo.helpdesk@jrc.it

By mail to:

CEO Help Desk
CEO, TP441
Space Applications Institute
Joint Research Centre
21020 ISPRA (VA)
ITALY

You may also telephone +39 332 785425 or fax to +39 332 785461.

For more general information on the CEO programme and Earth Observation related activities in Europe and world-wide please access the CEO web site at '<http://www.ceo.org>'.

7 References

- [1] Recommended Formats for the CEO Metadata, CEO/US/1400/231
- [2] Survey of current practices and standards for metadata management; Volume A: Survey and analysis of practices of 20 EU Organisations, CEO/US/1400/217
- [3] Survey of current practices and standards for metadata management; Volume B: Reference Document for major metadata standards & initiatives, major metadata attribute sets, CEO/US/1400/218
- [4] User Requirements Document, CEO/172/1995

Note All referenced documents are available at the CEO Web site at '<http://www.ceo.org>' under 'CEO Documents '.